

TRENDS AND MOTIVES IN THE POST-GRADUATE PROFESSIONAL ORIENTATION OF THE YOUNG DOCTORS OF THE 2025 CLASS OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITY-SOFIA

*Kirkov V.K.,
Leventi N.S.*

*Department of Social and Preventive Medicine and Disaster medicine
Faculty of Public Health "Prof. Tzecomir Vodenitcharov, MD, DMSc"
Medical University - Sofia*

ABSTRACT

The grown-up individual's need for self-affirmation is a unified whole with his professional and labor activity and with the successful realization in it. For this reason, professional choice is a complex decision-making process, determined by social and personal factors, as it is dictated not only by the needs of society, but also by the interests, opportunities, needs and inclinations of the individual. In view of this, the present article will present and analyze data from an empirical study investigating the trends, motives and conditions in the professional orientation of young doctors of the 2025 Class of Medical university-Sofia.

Keywords: trends, motives, young doctors, professional development.

INTRODUCTION

The professional division of labor arose in order to achieve the fullest use of people through their professional specialization, which in turn leads to the further development of the profession and professional differentiation. The profession represents a set of specialized and generalized functions, or knowledge, skills, work habits and formed abilities acquired through training or work, through which a person realizes himself, performing a socially useful service, determining his place in the social structure. [18, 5]

The grown-up individual's need for self-affirmation is a unified whole with his professional and labor activity and with the successful realization in it. For this reason, professional choice is a complex decision-making process, determined by social and personal factors, as it is dictated not only by the needs of society, but also by the interests, opportunities, needs and inclinations of the individual.

The choice of a profession predetermines to a large extent the life path of an individual, the development of his individual qualities and abilities, the unfolding of his essential powers, his realization as a working and social being. The labor and professional path affects the overall social behavior and social activity of the person. Educational and professional plans are the most important components of youth life plans. [18, 19, 20]

The uniqueness of the medical profession has been known since Antiquity, when the Father of Medicine, Hippocrates, in his writings "On Good Conduct" and "On the Physician" listed the rich palette of cognitive, temperamental, emotional and character qualities that a good doctor must possess. Individuals who choose the medical profession face specific professional requirements that shape their personality much more fully only when this choice meets the opportunities and interests of young people. [20, 5]

The training of future young doctors in higher medical schools in the Republic of Bulgaria is a six-year course and is regulated by the Ordinance on the Uniform State Requirements for the Acquisition of Higher Education in the Specialty "Medicine" and is conducted in accordance with the Law on Higher Education, the Law on development of the academic staff

in the Republic of Bulgaria and the internal normative documents of the relevant medical university. [1, 2] The training of the medical personnel does not end with their student training, during which they acquire theoretical and practical knowledge and skills and thus build labor and theoretical training for independently solving organizational, prophylactic, treatment-diagnostic and other professional tasks. [1, 5, 6] The medical profession provides a rich opportunity for young doctors after completing their student education for postgraduate training, thus realizing the professional differentiation among doctors to ensure meeting the current and future health needs of Bulgarians citizens.

The **PURPOSE** of this article is to present and analyze the trends, motives and expectations of the young doctors of the 2025 Class of Medical university-Sofia for their post-graduate professional development.

To fulfill the goal, the following **TASKS** were set and studied:

- ✓ Research and analysis of the wishes of young doctors when choosing a specialty after completing their student studies;
- ✓ Study of the expectations of young doctors for their future realization and the prerequisites for this;
- ✓ Establishing the reasons and conditions for choosing the postgraduate professional qualification of young doctors;

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The object of the study is the graduating students in medicine. The technical unit of observation is Medical University - Sofia. A questionnaire survey was distributed among the young doctors of the 2025 Class.

The study was conducted during the October 2025 – December 2025 period in the city of Sofia and included 243 young medical doctors.

A wide range of **sociological and statistical methods** are used in the survey: documentary method; questionnaire survey method - medical students from MU-Sofia were surveyed with an independently developed questionnaire card; descriptive analysis; analysis of variance; Pearson's χ^2 test; graphical analysis - for visualizing the results obtained. The indicators were assessed at $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance.

The quantitative analyses were performed with the SPSS 17.0 statistical software package. MICROSOFT OFFICE products were used for tabular and graphical processing and presentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To investigate trends among young physicians from the Class of 2025 at the Medical University of Sofia regarding their choice of specialty for postgraduate training, the first question of the survey was administered. The results presented in Table 1 indicate that the most preferred specialty is Anesthesiology and Intensive Care (10.78%), followed by Pediatrics (10.29%).

Among the surgical specialties, young physicians demonstrate the greatest interest in General Surgery (8.33%), as well as in Obstetrics and Gynecology and Orthopedics and Traumatology, each accounting for 4.90%.

With respect to the therapeutic specialties, Table 1 shows that the most preferred fields among newly graduated physicians are Endocrinology (5.63%), Cardiology (4.90%), Neurology (3.75%), and Psychiatry (2.94%). It is noteworthy that young physicians from the Class of 2025 also express interest in Ophthalmology and Dermatology and Venereology. At the same time, the proportion of respondents who would choose Internal Medicine is relatively low compared to previous years (2.45%).

The trend toward pursuing primary health care remains relatively stable, with 2.945% of respondents selecting General Medicine /Family Medicine/. A total of

4.45% of participants reported that they had not yet decided which specialty within the healthcare sector they would pursue.

The planning of physicians' professional and career development is a complex process influenced by multiple determinants. Among young physicians, the leading determinants in specialty choice include, on the one hand, economic factors—namely, the opportunities provided by a given specialty for additional employment and income in private outpatient practice or in ambulatory care [10, 5]. On the other hand, determinants such as gender and personal interests in a given specialty also play a significant role, as it has been demonstrated that different medical specialties require diverse sets of skills and attributes that physicians must possess and exhibit. For example, most surgical specialties require greater-than-average physical endurance due to high workload and the unpredictability of operative duration, which has traditionally led to their characterization as “demanding” or “male-dominated.”

A third group of determinants relates to working conditions, particularly the balance between personal and professional life. These factors are of critical importance, given that certain specialties are associated with heavy workloads, demanding on-call duties—including both daytime and night shifts—and work performed in both hospital and outpatient settings. Altogether, these characteristics define such specialties as burdensome to the psycho-emotional well-being of the individual, which, in turn, inevitably affects the physician's family and social environment. [10, 7, 4, 5]

Table 1.

In which field of medicine do you intend to specialize after completing your higher education?

Response	2025
Anesthesiology and Intensive Care	10.78%
Pediatrics	10.29%
Surgery	8.33%
Ophthalmology	5.88%
Endocrinology	5.63%
Dermatology	5.39%
Cardiology	4.90%
Obstetrics and Gynecology	4.90%
Orthopedics and Traumatology	4.90%
Diagnostic Imaging	3.43%
Urology	3.43%
Neurology	3.75%
General Medicine	2.94%
Psychiatry	2.94%
Gastroenterology	2.45%
Internal medicine	2.45%
Oncology	1.96%
Pathology	1.96%
Pulmonology	1.96%
Infectious Diseases	1.47%
Rheumatology	1.47%
Other/Undecided	4.45%

The second question of the survey examines young physicians' expectations regarding their future career development. The analysis of the data presented in Table 2 indicates that nearly 85% of respondents envision themselves working as physicians in clinical practice. Approximately 11% of the surveyed individuals expect to pursue careers as general practitioners or specialists in outpatient primary care.

Less than 1% of the study participants intend to develop as researchers, which would require them to continue their professional activity within a university

hospital setting and to undergo a competitive selection process for obtaining an academic position at a higher medical institution, or alternatively to pursue careers as academic teaching and research staff within non-clinical departments of medical universities.

Around 2% of respondents see their professional realization as medical representatives for pharmaceutical companies, while slightly over 1% would pursue careers within governmental health institutions, engaged in the organization of the healthcare system as well as in addressing trends and challenges in public health.

Table 2.

How do you envision your future professional realization?

Response	2025
As a physician in clinical practice	84.28%
As a physician in outpatient care (GP, specialist)	11.35%
As a researcher	0.87%
As a medical representative for a pharmaceutical company	2.18%
In an administrative structure (Ministry of Health, NHIF, etc.)	1.31%

To explore respondents' expectations regarding whether they would achieve better professional realization in Bulgaria or abroad, a third question was included in the survey. The results indicate that the majority of respondents (69.00%) believe they would achieve better career development if they continue their

professional path in Bulgaria, whereas 31.00% hold the opposite view (Table 3).

The analysis of these data suggests a reversal of the trend observed over the past decade, during which more than 50% of medical graduates in Bulgaria sought professional realization abroad.

Table 3.

In your opinion, where can you achieve better professional realization?

Response	2025
In Bulgaria	69.00%
Abroad (highly developed EU countries and the USA)	31.00%

In order to clarify the motivations among the group of young physicians who expressed a desire to pursue their careers in Bulgaria, a subsequent question was included in the empirical study. The analysis of the data presented in Table 4 shows that the leading reasons for this preference are "Family and friends" (33.45%) and "National identity and moral obligation to Bulgaria" (29.58%). These findings reflect, on the one hand, a perceived moral responsibility toward the home country, which has invested in their education and professional development, ensuring the future provision of healthcare services to Bulgarian society, and on the other hand, the importance of family and social environment.

Notably, a substantial proportion of respondents within this group (28.76%) also identify the "easier professional development in Bulgaria" as a key factor, indicating favorable opportunities for career advancement within the Bulgarian healthcare system.

To further investigate the motivations among the considerable proportion of young physicians who prefer professional realization abroad, an additional question was included in the study. The data presented in Table 5 indicate that the leading motive is "better financial remuneration" (approximately 43%), highlighting the importance of economic determinants. This is followed by "better organization of the healthcare system" in highly developed EU countries and the USA (just over 20%). Furthermore, 14.86% of respondents identify "a higher level of medical science and practice" as a motivating factor, while an equal proportion (14.86%) point to the "more difficult professional development in Bulgaria" as a reason for seeking opportunities abroad. Approximately 6.50% of respondents cite the "better standard of living abroad" as their primary motivation.

Table 4.

Your desire to pursue professional realization in Bulgaria is due to:

Response	2025
Family and friends	33.45%
National identity and moral obligation to Bulgaria	29.58%
Professional development in Bulgaria is significantly easier	28.76%
Better quality life in Bulgaria	3.45%
Higher level of medicine science and practice	2.79%
Other	1.97%

Table 5.

Your desire to pursue professional realization abroad is due to:

Response	2025
Better financial remuneration	42.45%
Better organization of the healthcare system	20.79%
Professional development in Bulgaria is significantly difficult	14.86%
Higher level of medicine science and practice	14.86%
Better quality life abroad	6.45%
Other	0.59%

The final question of the empirical study examines and analyzes the opinions of young physicians from the Class of 2025 at the Medical University of Sofia regarding the conditions necessary for their successful professional realization. As shown in Table 6, approximately half of the respondents (49.45%) identify “high-quality education” as the leading condition, encompassing material and technical facilities, teaching staff, and curricula.

Approximately 1/3 of respondents (35.75%) indicate “motivation and willingness” as the key factor,

while 14.80% identify “perseverance and patience” as essential for successful professional realization.

The analysis of these data suggests that the development of medical professionals is a complex process that integrates both individual qualities and preferences, as well as numerous social determinants that are beyond the direct control of young physicians and are instead shaped by the respective state, through the organization of the healthcare system and the structure of higher medical education.

Table 6.

In your opinion, what is the most important condition for successful professional realization?

Response	2025
High-quality education (facilities, teaching staff, curricula)	49.45%
Motivation and willingness	35.75%
Perseverance and patience	14.80%

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of the empirical study on the conditions and trends in the career development of young physicians from the Class of 2025 at the Medical University of Sofia, it can be concluded that professional orientation is a multifactorial process that integrates both individual characteristics and preferences, as well as a wide range of societal determinants.

Evidence from the analysis indicates that a larger proportion of young physicians envision their professional careers in Bulgaria. A notable decline (approximately one-third of the total share) is observed in the previously established trend over the past decade, whereby more than half of newly graduated physicians sought professional realization abroad. Among those who still prefer to work abroad, economic determinants remain the leading motivating factors.

A substantial proportion of respondents in the study intend to pursue careers in clinical practice, selecting specialties in accordance with their personal characteristics. These choices reflect a dual objective: achieving a balance between professional responsibilities and personal life, while also securing opportunities for additional employment and income in private and outpatient medical practice.

The quality of human capital within the healthcare system is largely determined by the level of professional education and training. There exists a strong relationship between the degree of training, the potential, and the competitiveness of medical professionals, and the overall performance of the healthcare system, whose primary function is to meet the current and future health needs of the population.

Therefore, ensuring the training and development of highly qualified medical professionals is of strategic

importance for society. This is essential for the delivery of healthcare services grounded in the highest standards of medical knowledge and clinical practice, aligned with ethical principles and norms, and based on scientific evidence.

References

1. Kirkov V (2023), A training quality optimisation model for the undergraduate internship in Medical university – Sofia, Sofia 2023. PhD Thesis, Medical University of Sofia.
2. Kirkov V, Zlatanova-Velikova R, Vodenicharova AI, Leventi N (2022) Quality of the practical education during undergraduate internship at the Medical university Sofia. *Acta Medica Bulgarica Journal*, Vol. XLIX 4/2022, ISSN: 0324-1750, p.48-53
3. Kirkov V, Zlatanova-Velikova R (2022) Approaches and methods for quality assurance of medical education in Bulgaria regulated in normativ documents. *Man, society medicine, Kardzhali*, 2022, ISBN 978-954-652-037-1, pp. 380-386
4. Kirkov V (2024), The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the quality of higher medical education, <https://pharmacia.pensoft.net/issue/4722/>
5. Kirkov V, Vodenicharova A, Ivanova K, Markova K (2024) Trends and motives in the postgraduate professional orientation of the young doctors of the 2023 class of Medical University-Sofia. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e138245>
6. Kirkov V (2025) Trends in postgraduate professional orientation of young doctors graduated from the Medical University-Sofia. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e146974>
7. Kumwenda B, Cleland J, Prescott G, Walker K, Johnston P (2019). Relationship between sociodemographic factors and specialty destination of UK trainee doctors: a national cohort study. *BMJ Open* 2019;9:e026961. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2018-026961
8. Law on Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria (2020)
9. Papanou M, Routsis E, Tsamakis K, Fotis L, Marinos G, Lidoriki I, Karamanou M, Papaioannou T G, Tsipsis D, Smyrnis N, Rizos E, Schizas D (2021) Medical education challenges and innovations during COVID-19 pandemic. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*, Volume 98, Issue 1159, May 2022, Pages 321–327, <https://doi.org/10.1136/postgradmedj-2021-140032>
10. Michalik B, Kulbat M, Domagała A (2024) Factors affecting young doctors' choice of medical specialty-A qualitative study, *PLoS One* 2024 Feb 1;19(2):e0297927., doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0297927
11. Ministry of health – Republic of Bulgaria. National Health Strategy 2021-2030 (2021)<https://www.mh.government.bg/bg/politiki/strategii-i-kontseptsii/strategii/proekt-na-nacionalna-zdravna-strategiya-2030/>
12. Regulation No. 1 (2015) On acquiring a specialty in the health care system of the Council of Ministers, 13.06.2023
13. Regulations for the organization and activities of Medical University-Sofia, <https://mu-sofia.bg/za-universiteta/normativni-dokumenti/pravilnici-mu/> found on 01.05.2024
14. Regulations for the organization and conduct of educational practices and internships at Sofia University <https://mu-sofia.bg/za-universiteta/normativni-dokumenti/pravilnici-mu/> found on 01.05.2024
15. Soethout MBM, Heymans MW, Olle J (2008) Career preference and medical students' biographical characteristics and academic achievement, *Medical Teacher* 2008;30:1, e15–e22, doi: 10.1080/01421590701759614
16. Southworth E & Gleason SH (2021) COVID 19: A Cause for Pause in Undergraduate Medical Education and Catalyst for Innovation; *HEC Forum*; Published: 22 January 2021; Volume 33, pages 125–142, DOI: [10.1007/s10730-020-09433-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10730-020-09433-5)
17. Vodenitcharov Tz (2018) Beyond the Limits of the Possible. GorexPress
18. Vodenitcharov Tz (1986) Profession doctor. *Medicine and physical education*
19. Vodenitcharov Tz, Borisov V (2021) The Public Health Phenomenon in a Changing World, Second Revised Edition. Gorex Press, ISBN 978-954-616-311-0, c. 229
20. Vodenitcharov Tz (1992) Way in medicine, Sofia
21. WHO. The Global Action Plan for Healthy Lives and Well-being for All (SDG3 GAP), (2019). <https://www.who.int/initiatives/sdg3-global-action-plan>